
SWOC ANALYSIS OF PRANAVA SOUHARDA SAHAKARI LTD.- A CASE STUDY**Shilpa. K*1, C.K. Hebbar*2**

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The study focus is to understand the Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd operations.

Design: Secondary data is collected from published papers, books and websites from google scholar, bank website and research gate. Further, the bank is analysed using SWOC analysis.

Findings: Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd. Is a cooperative bank which caters the needs of many businessmen, localities, and community in large by providing good banking services.

Originality: The study highlights the prospects of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd and provides suggestions for further improvements.

Paper Type: Company Case Study

Keywords: Cooperative Bank, Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd ,Organisation Structure, Products And Services, SWOC Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

To help the ordinary people who lack financial support, cooperative banks are crucial. Every bank must operate effectively and with financial stability [1]. Cooperative banks have the effect of ensuring economic improvement. Cooperative banks must function because they are the guardians of public funds; as a result, they must be productive and profitable [2]. According to the National Association for Cooperative Urban Banks (NAFCUB), cooperative banks' overall deposits and lending outpace both new and old private sector banks [3]. The first co-operative credit societies Act was passed in 1904. This law permits the creation of credit organizations in both urban and rural areas so that the average person can access loans at more affordable rates [4]. It goes back to the second half of the year 2014 where in a group of like-minded friends got together on the initiative of Shri G R Prasad to form a Co-Operative society under Karnataka Souharda Societies Act 1997. The idea behind co-operative banks is to support and encourage.

- Self-Employment.
- SAVAYAVA – Organic Cultivation.
- Provide Financial Support to Small and Micro Units and
- Solar Power Usage.

These four S remain the focus area for PRANAVA and the organisation has done a lot of work in this direction especially encouraging the youngsters from the colleges to become job creators rather than job seekers. Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd is a cooperative bank, established in 2015 at Yeyyadi, Mangalore. This study attempts to highlight the Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd operations. Co-operative banks in India are more than 100 years old. They came into existence with the enactment of Co-operative Credit Societies Act, 1904 [5]. Relationship lending typically forms the foundation of the banking business model, which is centered on traditional intermediation. Financing decisions are heavily influenced by soft information, or qualitative and private information about customers, which banks can collect and manage by leveraging their territorial rootedness [6]. Depending on the risk profile of the banks, different regulations have different implications [7]. The Co-operative Bank's tactic of enticing clients to contact its account management center through phone or letter rather than the branches worked well [8].

II. RELATED WORKS

Below Table 1 shows systematic literature of review is conducted from 2003 to 2021 by using the keywords "co-operative bank", "UCBs" from google scholar and research gate.

Table 1: Related works on Co-operative banks.

S. No	Focus	Outcome	Reference
1	To research whether a cooperative bank's size affects its effectiveness.	The method of instalment repayment is acceptable to customers.	Gupta, J., & Jain, S. (2012) [9].
2	Financial stability and stress resistance of cooperative banks.	the idea that as a result of characteristics of their business model, cooperative banks are comparatively less capable of responding to stress.	Hesse, H., & Čihák, M. (2007) [10].
3	For cooperative banks, the participation of outside directors has a considerable impact on efficiency metrics, whereas such factors have no meaningful impact for stock banks.	The findings imply that cooperative banks require outside directors' discipline more than stock banks, which are subject to intense shareholder pressure.	Yamori, N., Harimaya, K., & Tomimura, K. (2017) [11].
4	Small financial institutions have a uniform business plan, and the state of their local markets' economies has a significant impact on how well they succeed. The heterogeneity of the environmental conditions must be taken into consideration during the efficiency measurement.	Environment has a significant impact on efficiency estimations. Banks in the northeast of Italy are found to be more cost-efficient, taking advantage of a favourable environment, whereas banks in the south of Italy exhibit a higher profit efficiency, perhaps as a result of less intense competitive pressure.	Battaglia, F., Farina, V., Fiordelisi, F., & Ricci, O. (2010) [12].
5	Analyze how NPA affects bank tasks.	The analysis also shows that the primary NPA structures are based on the required government need components.	Haralayya, B. (2021) [13].
6	The current HRM procedures at Indian cooperative banks with regard to elements like hiring and firing, training and development, performance reviews, promotions, pay, and	The correct system of HR rules and practises must be in place for a business to effectively hire, select, develop, appraise, compensate, place, promote, or fire personnel.	Ramu, N. (2008) [14].

	employer-employee relationships		
7	Co-operatives are businesses that are collaboratively managed and democratically controlled by organized groups of people.	Accordingly, cooperative corporate governance aims to ensure the performance of the cooperative by involving members, management, and staff in the formulation of policy, strategy, and decision-making processes.	Kamesam, V. (2002) [15].
8	A distinctive system of share capital connected to borrowing in UCBs has been created as a result of the member's participation principle.	The Banking systems should rise above the difficulties rather than succumb to them, meet them head-on, and take advantage of the fresh opportunities.	Ramu, N. (2006) [16].
9	Beyond a certain point, the democratic nature of cooperative banks and the level of their professional management increased the quality of overall governance.	The significance of board independence for efficient governance was confirmed by the identification of criteria like lower instances of board members serving more than two consecutive terms and lower or no family member presence as major differentiators for banks with excellent governance ratings.	Srivastava, D. A., & Kumar, A. (2021) [17].
10	The development and spread of financial cooperatives, network configurations, business models, relationship banking, balancing member interests, taxation, and legal and regulatory frameworks.	Efficiency and sustainability, mergers, acquisitions, and failures; the advantages (and difficulties) of FinTech; and the value that financial cooperatives bring to the real economy, even in difficult times.	McKillop, D., French, D., Quinn, B., Sobiech, A. L., & Wilson, J. O. (2020) [18].
11	To determine various financial ratios.	The OER in the banking system is determined by dividing all operating costs by all advances.	Sharma, M. R. G.(2019) [19].
12	The primary goals of the "LOANS AND ADVANCES" Cooperative Bank study were to examine the various loan and advance programmes used by the bank.	Unsecured loan is defined as "a Loan or advance not so secured" in Section 5(1)(n) of the Banking Regulation Act.	Haralayya, B. (2021) [20].
13	The most important	A successful manager or secretary will	Anbumani, K. (2007)

	and difficult task to complete is grabbing the interest of customers or a member participant.	instantly get member participation if he is allowed to take whatever action he believes is best for growth and success and can demonstrate that his firm is successful.	[21].
14	An organization's net profit or loss for a certain time period is displayed in the profit and loss account.	Financial statement analysis is essential since it assists demonstrate the financial situation based on historical and current data.	Orlitzky, M., Schmidt, F. L., & Rynes, S. L. (2003) [22].
15	Advances are sums of money that banks give to organizations to meet their short-term financial needs.	Loans are a type of debt, whereas bank advances are credit facilities.	Ramu, N. (2006) [23].

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- (1) To study the overview of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd.
- (2) To understand the organization structure of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd.
- (3) To identify the Products and Services offered by Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd.
- (4) To assess the marketing strategy of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd.
- (5) To analyze the Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd using SWOC analysis.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Secondary data is collected from published scholarly articles, bank website and books from google scholar and research gate. Further, the study analyzed Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd bank using SWOC analysis.

PRANAVA SOUHARDA SAHAKARI LTD- AN OVERVIEW :

The organization is a dream child of Mr. G.R. Prasad who has made this organization to come up in the year 2014. The four S inculcates to support self-employment, SAVAYAVA (organic cultivation), supporting financially to small and micro units and solar power usage. These four S remain the focus area for PRANAVA and the organisation has done a lot of work in this direction especially encouraging the youngsters from the colleges to become job creators rather than job seekers. The inauguration of the PRANAVA SOUHARDA SAHAKARI Ltd (PSSL) was held on 18th of January 2015 with his holy presence and blessings of Sri Sri Gurudevnananda Swamiji of Odiyoor in the presence of the Honourable Forest Minister and also the district in charge Minister of Karnataka State Government Shri Ramanatha Rai. The function was presided by the then Mayor of Mangaluru City Shri Mahabala Marla. The dignitaries on the dias included Shri Krishna Palemar Ex Minister of Karnataka Government, Shri Ravichandran - CMD of Diya Systems Mangaluru. Its headquarters is located in Yeyyadi, Mangaluru and it consists of six branches located in outskirts of Mangaluru.

The organisation was started as a business entity for doing banking activities with an ideology of FINANCIAL SUPERMARKET UNDER ONE ROOF on business front with social commitment keeping the four S as Focussed Area.

Vision Of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd.

To have National presence in banking activities by NEXT DECADE , to provide a Financial solution of all kinds, to the needy with focussed area as a base and a part of our commitment to fulfil the social responsibility.

Mission of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd.

Achieve the set goal with a professional approach on the back drop of FOCUSED AREA as social commitment.

ORGANIZATION STRUCTURE :

Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd has the following organization structure exhibited in figure 1.

Pranava has completed its five years very successfully. It was challenging as well as rewarding journey. Challenging because the economies are passing through a rough patch. We believe that its cyclical and a clear

structural change is happening in case of Indian economy. Indian Economy has remained robust and attractive destination for investment.

Figure 1: Organisation Structure of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd

Source: Author

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES :

Drawing, making, accepting, discounting, selling, buying, collecting, and dealing in draughts, certificates, and other securities [24].

1. Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd & Loans:

- Mortgage loan
- Personal Loan
- Jewellery Loan
- Car Loan
- Bike Loan
- Loan on Deposit

2. Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd & Services:

- Daily Savings
- E Stamping
- Monthly RD

- Term Deposits
- RTGS and NEFT
- Monthly Transfer facility
- 3. Other Services
 - D'Mat and Trading Account.
 - Health Insurance and General Insurance Products.
 - Advice on Mutual Fund and Life Insurance Products.
 - Domestic and International Money Transfer.
 - LIC Premium Collection.
 - E-Ticketing (Bus, Train, Air and Tour Packages).

MARKETING STRATEGY :

- (1) Have organised SELF EMPLOYMENT FAIR for the first time in Mangaluru.
- (2) Have conducted medical and blood donation camps in YEYYADI and VAMANJOOR.
- (3) Done Workshops for the students of different colleges in their campus on self-employment in and around Mangaluru.
- (4) Arranged Four Workshops for different Mahila mandalas one exclusively for SC&STgroup.
- (5) Yoga classes and presentation on health-related issues.
- (6) Presentations of SAVAYAVA –organic cultivation is done for the members also to the public.

SWOC Analysis :

The most well-known instrument for auditing and analysing the overall strategic position of the company and its surroundings is SWOC Analysis [25]. The most popular method for tracking and evaluating a company's overall competitive role and climate is called SWOC Analysis [26]. SWOC is a low-cost tool for conducting a business analysis [27]. SWOC analysis is a method used to comprehend how internal and external factors affect a company's entire operations, products, or strategy in order to better plan and make decisions [28]. In order to match the firm's resources and capabilities to the competitive environment in which it works, information from the SWOC analysis is helpful [29]. Issues like the government's provision of subsidies are addressed through strength [30].

Figure 2: lists the SWOC analysis of Pranava Souharda Sahakari Ltd.

V. FINDINGS

- (1) The first Self Employment Fair has been held in Mangaluru.
- (2) Have held blood donation and medical camps in YEYYADI and VAMANJOOR.
- (3) Planned Four workshops for various Mahila mandalas, one of which was reserved specifically for SC&ST group.
- (4) SAVAYAVA organic cultivation is presented to the public and to members of the organisation.
- (5) The bank is profitable across all of its branches.
- (6) Large-scale medium-term mortgage loans are offered by the bank. Short-term unsecured loan percentage is the lowest. The percentage of long-term mortgage loans is also decreasing at the same time.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

- (1) When in doubt, the Bank should provide the office in accordance with RBI rules, however it does not.
- (2) Credit securitization is necessary.
- (3) The credit withdrawal company should regularly evaluate the customer's financial situation.
- (4) Banks should make every effort to deal with the NPA.

VII. CONCLUSION

A cooperative bank is a financial institution that is owned by its members, who also double as the bank's owners and clients. People with a same interest from the same local or professional community frequently found it. It was established to support the social uplift of economically underprivileged groups and to shield them from the grasp of predatory lenders who give out loans to the needy at exorbitant interest rates. The ideas of cooperation, mutual aid, democratic decision-making, and open membership inform the co-operative structure's design. It refers to the "no profit, no loss" and "one shareholder, one vote" concepts.

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